

Report on Zoonoses, Alimentary and Water-Borne Infections in the Slovak Republic for 2024

1. *Salmonella* spp.

Salmonella has been an important zoonotic pathogen for both humans and animals for a long time. Disease symptoms include nausea, diarrhoea, fever and abdominal cramps 12 to 72 hours after the onset of infection. Symptoms usually last from 4 to 7 days. The main sources of disease are eggs or undercooked or re-contaminated food products of animal origin, especially poultry meat. As the keeping of reptiles and exotic animals becomes more widespread, so does the risk of salmonellosis caused by the rare serovars of *Salmonella* spp. In 2023, 77,486 people contracted the disease in European Union countries, and 88 cases resulted in death. A total of 1,115 epidemics were reported. Similar as in the previous year, Slovakia and the Czech Republic reported their highest rates in 2023.

In 2024, 4,087 cases from the A02 diagnosis group were reported in Slovakia, of which 4,023 were salmonellosis cases (A02.0, A02.1, A02.2, A02.8, A02.9). The incidence is lower by 2% compared to 2023 and lower by 5% compared to the five-year average. Salmonellosis trends have been declining over the past 20 years. Cases were reported from every region of Slovakia, and the highest incidence was recorded in the Prešov, Košice, and Trnava regions. The lowest incidence was observed in the Trenčín and Banská Bystrica regions. The pattern of occurrence was sporadic and familial, but also epidemic. There were 133 epidemics reported, including 15 major epidemics. In 100 cases of epidemics these were family outbreaks, with between two and four cases per family. The most common aetiology of the disease and the outbreaks was *Salmonella* Enteritidis. No deaths were reported in the group of salmonella infections in 2024.

**Incidence of salmonellosis (A02).aa
20-year trend
2024, SR.**

Fig. 1 The 20-year trend of Salmonellosis in Slovakia

In 2024, the inspection authorities tested 12,043 food samples, and 0.24% were positive, compared to 0.54% in the previous year. Higher percentages of positive samples were found in unspecified poultry meat (6.84%), broiler meat (*Gallus gallus*) (5.38%) and eggs (1.74%). Of the 203 red meat samples tested, two pork samples were positive, with the identified serovars of *S. Typhimurium* and *S. Typhimurium* monophasic, 1 positive sample of pork and beef, with

the identified serovar of *S. Infantis*, and 1 positive sample of mixed meat, meat products – heat-treated, for direct consumption, with the identified serovar of *S. Derby*. No *Salmonella* spp. was found in the other samples of beef, other animal meats, or raw minced meat intended for direct consumption.

Among 72 samples of cheese made from sheep's milk, *S. Derby* was detected in 1 case. Among 171 samples of raw fruit and vegetables tested, 1 case of *S. Livingstone* was detected. There was no *Salmonella* spp. found in the 52 egg samples tested, unlike in 2023, when 5.37% of samples were found to be positive for *Salmonella* spp. In 2024, no *Salmonella* spp. was found in 778 samples of confectionery products examined (0.53% positive samples in 2023), or in 653 samples of delicatessen products examined (0.09% positive samples in 2023). In 9,674 samples of other foods tested, *Salmonella* spp. was also not found.

During 2024, a total of 5,890 clinical animal samples were screened for the presence of *Salmonella* spp. A total of 4,438 poultry flocks were screened with 1.24% of them found to be positive. The predominant serovar was *Salmonella infantis* (35 x), followed by *S. enteritidis* (14 x). In livestock, 272 samples from cattle were examined, with salmonella found in 3.8% of cases. In sheep, 6.2% of the 81 samples examined were found to be positive for *Salmonella*. In pigs, 3.4% of the 59 samples examined were found to contain *Salmonella*. In horses, 1 of the 28 samples examined was found to be positive for the presence of salmonella. In the group of pets, dominated by the testing of dogs, 3.3% of 487 samples were found to be positive. In cats, 118 samples were tested, with 1.7% positive. The dominant serovar was *S. Enteritidis*. In the group of reptiles (zoo animals/pets) and snakes (zoo animals), 47.4% of 19 samples were found positive for findings of salmonella. Two positive samples were reported in hedgehogs (zoo animals) and other zoo animals, and one positive sample was reported in other carnivores (zoo animals) and turtles. The remaining 44 samples from other animals screened were without positive findings. The prevalence was 3% among birds other than poultry. The predominant serovars were *S. Typhimurium*, *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Enterica* sk. B. Of the total of 5,890 clinical samples from animals screened, 112 were positive, which represents 1.9%. The proportion of positive samples out of the total number of clinical samples screened was found in broiler poultry, namely 34.9%. It was dominated by the serovars *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium*.

In 2024, a total of 397 samples of feed or compound feed were screened for the presence of *Salmonella* spp. Prevalence data are divided into four groups: feed mixes, feed of animal origin, feed of plant origin, and other feed. In 122 samples of feed mixes, *S. Mbandaka* was confirmed in 1 sample. In 185 samples of animal origin feed, in 89 samples of feed of plant origin and in 1 sample of other feed, no positive detection of *Salmonella* spp. was confirmed.

Among the 7,095 water and environmental samples screened, 59 (0.83%) were positive for *Salmonella* spp.

In 2024, the microbial resistance profile was established for 47 *Salmonella* spp. isolates obtained under national inspection programmes for *Salmonella* infections in flocks of domestic fowl (*Gallus gallus*), turkeys and laying hens and 18 isolates obtained under the process hygiene criterion 2.1.5 verification, and under the Commission Regulation (EC) No. 2073/2005 on microbiological criteria for foodstuffs. Upon comparing animal and food isolates, no differences were found. The trend of microbial resistance in *Salmonella* spp. isolates isolated from different matrices shows a long-standing equilibrium, with a higher level of minimal inhibitory concentration for antimicrobials from the group of tetracyclines, quinolones and their derivatives. The results correlate with data from neighbouring European countries.

2. *Escherichia coli*

Escherichia (E.) coli forms the predominant component of the microbiome of the gastrointestinal tract of humans and warm-blooded animals. It colonises the gastrointestinal tract in early life and occurs predominantly as a harmless commensal. Despite its widespread distribution in the environment, its presence in certain components

of the environment is increasingly considered as a significant indicator of faecal contamination. In addition to commensal types, disease-causing types of pathogenic *E. coli* are also known. For the majority of diarrhoeal *E. coli* (from English *diarrhoeagenic E. coli*, DEC) a human is a reservoir, and infections occur via the faecal-oral route, which is particularly common in developing countries or in areas where sanitation is generally poor. The exception in this case is Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC), which is classified as a zoonotic pathogen. Animals are the reservoir, and infection is most often associated with consumption of undercooked contaminated food, but there is also a high probability of contracting the disease after contact with an infected animal. STEC is characterised by the production of the Shiga toxin, and the infection often causes gastroenteritis, enterocolitis, bloody diarrhoea and in some cases haemolytic-uremic syndrome (HUS). The incubation period is 3 to 9 days.

In 2022, STEC became the third most frequently reported foodborne zoonosis in the European Union and European Economic Area (EU/EEA) countries, but in 2023, there was an increase of up to 22% in confirmed infections. According to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), STEC is also the third most common bacterial agent causing epidemics resulting from the consumption of contaminated water or food. In 2023, the highest number of cases and the highest reporting rate since the start of monitoring (2007) of STEC in the EU were reported. In 2023, 29 countries reported a total of 10,901 confirmed cases of STEC infection. Despite the fact that serogroup has been proven to not be an indicator of pathogenicity, it is still one of the significant epidemiological markers indicating the circulation of pathogenic *E. coli* in the population. The most frequently reported serogroups in 2023 were O157 (19.8%), O26 (16.7%), O146 (5.7%), O103 (5.4%), O145 (4.5%), and O91 (4.0%).

There are two National Reference Laboratories in the EFSA network established in the Slovak Republic that focus on the detection of pathogenic *E. coli* – one is located at the Veterinary and Food Administration in Dolný Kubín and the other at the Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic in Bratislava.

During 2024, a total of 12,343 cases classified under A.04 – Other bacterial intestinal infections were reported, of which approximately 4.8% (597) were infections caused by pathogenic *E. coli*, with EPEC infection being the most common aetiology.

Laboratories of the Public Health Authority of the SR, Regional Public Health Authorities, Veterinary and Food Administrations, the Central Control and Testing Institute of Agriculture, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology of the Slovak University of Technology, the Water Management Research Institute, and the Food Research Institute examined a total of 31,193 samples of food, feed, fertilizers, water and the environment. Out of all samples, the presence of *E. coli* was detected in 5.6% of them.

In 2024, no Shiga toxin-producing *E. coli* (STEC/VTEC) in food was detected. The presence of O157 was detected in 17 cases in veterinary samples.

The resistance of *E. coli* to antibiotics was monitored in the NRL in Dolný Kubín because of microbial resistance, and in the laboratory of the Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology of the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava. While the NRL focused on testing samples of a veterinary origin, the laboratory of the Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology of the STU focuses on testing microbial resistance of *E. coli* in various food and water samples.

3. *Yersinia* spp.

The genus *Yersinia* (*Y.*) consists of 21 species, of which three are pathogenic for humans – *Yersinia* (*Y.*) *pestis*, which is transmitted by fleas and causes plague; *Y. pseudotuberculosis*, the aetiological factor of rodentiosis; and *Y. enterocolitica*, which mainly causes gastrointestinal disease. The main sources of risk factors for yersiniosis are raw, undercooked pork, poultry or meat products, but also fresh and unpasteurised milk, infected plants, tofu, seafood and polluted water. Food may be contaminated primarily or by contact with infected surfaces and equipment.

It can also be transmitted from person to person. Mostly young children are affected; the bacterium causes fever, abdominal pain, diarrhoea and even arthritis. In 2023, 8,738 cases of human yersiniosis were confirmed (651 hospitalised, i.e. 25.5%), which corresponds to a reporting rate in the European Union of 2.4 cases per 100,000 inhabitants. Compared to 2022 (2.2 per 100,000 inhabitants), this represents an increase of 13.5%. This was the highest number of cases and the highest reporting rate seen at the EU level in the last decade. The overall trend in *Yersinia* infection showed a statistically significant increase ($p < 0.01$) between 2019 and 2023. The prevalence of *Y. enterocolitica* was highest in fruit and vegetables (65.3%), meat and meat products (34.4%) and only (0.32%) in milk and dairy products.

A total of 261 cases were reported in 2024, which is up 10% compared to the previous year. The highest morbidity was reported in the age categories of 0 years and of 1 to 4 years. The diseases were reported from all regions, with the highest morbidity in the Prešov and Nitra regions and the lowest morbidity in the Žilina region. No deaths were reported.

During 2024, four cases of extraintestinal yersiniosis were reported. No deaths were reported.

A total of 49 clinical samples were tested for *Y. enterocolitica*, and no positive finding of *Y. enterocolitica* was confirmed, though in 1 case its presence was confirmed in dog faeces.

4. *Cronobacter* spp.

Cronobacter spp. is a genus of gram-negative facultatively anaerobic bacteria in the Enterobacteriaceae family, capable of growing in a wider temperature range (5 – 47°C), in a drier environment and surviving spray drying. Members of this genus cause rare but often fatal infections in infants, the most at-risk group being low-birth-weight newborns (below 2,500g); rarely, it can also cause invasive infection in adults and the elderly patients (immunocompromised and cancer patients). Disease symptoms include irritability, jaundice, hoarse breathing and fluctuating body temperature. Meningitis can develop. Up to 50% of newborn children may die within several hours or days. The main cause is contamination of dried infant formula with this pathogen, as the technologies used do not allow for the production of sterile dried infant formula. Seven EU Member States (Cyprus, Czechia, Hungary, Italy, Slovenia, Slovakia, and Spain) reported data on *Cronobacter* spp. for 2023 in “initial infant formula” and in “food intended for infants and young children” collected at the distributor’s level.

None of the 678 samples tested was positive. No samples were collected at the production level. Thirteen EU Member States reported data on *Cronobacter* spp. collected outside the scope of Commission Regulation (EC) No 2073/2005. The samples included “initial infant formula”, “foods intended for infants and young children”, and “dairy products other than cheese”. These samples were collected from retail outlets, processing plants, the wholesale level, or hospitals and healthcare facilities either for supervision or monitoring purposes. A total of 1,392 individual sampling units and 126 batches were tested. Only one sample (0.06%) – “milk product (other than cheese)–dried milk and whey powder” collected by Germany at a processing plant – had a positive result.

In 2024, no cases of these diseases were reported in humans.

A total of 1,107 samples of dried initial infant formula and follow-on formula were tested, and the presence of *Cronobacter* spp. was not confirmed in any of the samples tested.

5. *Shigella* spp.

The *Shigella* genus consists of rod-shaped bacteria belonging to the *Enterobacteriaceae* family and the *Enterobacteriales* order, which are the aetiological agents of the alimentary disease shigellosis, and which are pathogenic both for humans and primates. Shigellae have the capacity for adherence, invasiveness, intracellular reproduction and cell-to-cell spread. The incubation period takes from one to seven days, manifested by shivering, malaise, fever,

abdominal pain, and watery diarrhoea with mucus admixture. The illness may last from five to seven days. The infection is spread via the faecal-oral route and by direct contact with infected individuals, contaminated food, water or objects. Shigellae are very sensitive to both drying and common disinfectants. The most recent data available are for 2023, when 6,616 cases were reported from EU/EEA countries, representing an incidence of 1.93/100,000 population. Morbidity rates per 100,000 inhabitants above the European average were recorded in Luxembourg (5.9), France (5.66), Malta (5.59), Belgium (4.37), Slovakia (4.46), Ireland (3.57), and the Netherlands (3.12). The highest count of cases was reported by France (1,690).

In Slovakia, a long-term declining trend in the incidence of shigellosis has been observed. In 2024, a total of 172 cases of the sickness were reported, which represents a 25% decline compared to 2023 and an 8% increase compared to the five-year average. Two cases of carriage were recorded. The most common agent was *Shigella flexneri*. Cases were reported from every region of Slovakia, with the highest morbidity reported in the Prešov and Košice regions. The highest age-specific morbidity was reported in the age categories of 0 years and of 1 to 4 years. In total, there were three epidemics (12 patients), one major epidemic and two minor family epidemics.

In 2024, no food samples were tested for *Shigella* spp.

6. *Plesiomonas shigelloides*

The genus *Plesiomonas* is currently included in the family of *Enterobacteriaceae*, and it contains only one agent, *Plesiomonas shigelloides*, which was first isolated in 1947 from human faeces as the aetiological agent of an intestinal disease. Plesiomonads are ubiquitously spread, occurring in both fresh and salt water, with a higher incidence in tropical and subtropical zones. The primary reservoir is the aquatic environment, as well as soil and animals. Its clinical symptoms are fever, diarrhoea, abdominal pain, vomiting, nausea, chills and headache. The incubation period is up to 48 hours, and symptoms subside within two weeks. The infection spreads through the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, contaminated food, and also from human to human. Due to antigenic relatedness of *P. shigelloides* with *Shigella* spp., a scientific hypothesis has been put forward that plesiomonads naturally immunise the human population, and the frequency of *Shigella* spp. as an aetiological agent of diarrhoeal diseases is gradually declining.

In 2024, samples of surface water and the environment were purposely screened for the presence of *Plesiomonas shigelloides*. In 2024, one strain of *P. shigelloides* was isolated from a surface water sample, where the presence of *P. shigelloides* was confirmed.

7. *Legionella* spp.

Legionella bacteria are a part of freshwater microbial ecosystems. They live in symbiosis with other bacteria and amoebae, especially in biofilms. Optimum conditions for the survival and reproduction of *Legionella* bacteria are provided mainly by artificial water systems, such as building distribution systems and water park facilities. Researchers have thus far identified 61 species of *Legionella*, 28 of which were associated with human infections. Infection most commonly occurs through inhalation of contaminated water aerosol, less commonly through aspiration of contaminated water. The infection may have its course as an atypical pneumonia called Legionnaires' disease, as a flu-like illness called Pontiac fever, or asymptotically. Human-to-human transmission has not been confirmed. Legionnaires' disease is found mainly in men, individuals over 50 years of age, and individuals with risk factors such as smoking, alcohol abuse, chronic diseases, and immunosuppression. As part of the epidemiological investigations of cases, exposure to contaminated water is sought during the incubation period of 2 – 10 days before the onset of symptoms. Depending on the place of exposure, infections are classified as community-acquired, nosocomial, or travel-related. The incidence of Legionnaires' disease has been on an upward trend in EU/EEA countries since 2016, which

is related to improving diagnostics and surveillance of the disease, increasing average life expectancy, water system design, and maintenance and climate change.

In 2024, 107 cases of Legionnaires' disease were reported, representing an incidence rate of 1.9/100,000 and an increase by 30% compared to 2023. Pontiac fever was diagnosed in 61 patients. Diagnostics for Legionella infections, previously only available in Bratislava, have been expanded to 24 other cities. This development reflects growing awareness of the disease, better availability of diagnostics, and therefore a higher proportion of properly treated patients.

In 2024, a total of 1,131 samples of water, swabs from an aquatic environment, air, and swabs from air conditioning equipment were tested for the presence of Legionella in the environment. Legionella was detected in 22.5% of the samples tested.

Environmental testing to identify the source of infection was performed in 33 (31%) cases of Legionnaires' disease and in 6 (10%) patients with Pontiac fever.

8. *Vibrio* spp.

Vibrio is a genus of bacteria, which moves using a whip-like appendage. As pathogens, the most severe risk is associated with *Vibrio (V.) cholerae* serotypes O1 and O139, which produce the cholera toxin and cause cholera epidemics. In 2024, cholera epidemics were reported in several African and Asian countries, with the largest epidemics occurring in Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Congo, Ethiopia, and Nigeria. Thanks to rigorous hygiene, there has been no endemic disease in Europe for a long time, and it occurs only as an imported infection. In 2024, cholera was reported in several countries around the world, with Afghanistan, Iraq, Iran, Lebanon, Pakistan, Somalia, Sudan, Syria, and Yemen, i.e., countries experiencing current or ending military conflicts, where many people live in refugee camps with poor sanitary conditions and a shortage of drinking water. In this regard, no data are yet available from Ukraine, where cholera infections are expected to occur. Serotypes of *V. cholerae* non-O1/non-O139 were isolated from diarrhoeal diseases. Humans can be infected directly through the use of water intended for recreational purposes or through the food chain. The genus of *Vibrio* spp. also includes 12 other medically important species that cause disease in humans. Currently, the clinical significance of two species, *V. parahaemolyticus* and *V. vulnificus*, is growing. An increasing number of diseases caused by *V. parahaemolyticus* are reported in developing countries, especially among children, elderly people, pregnant women, and people with compromised immune systems. *V. parahaemolyticus* is becoming an emergent foodborne pathogen causing severe gastroenteritis. Infection occurs when contaminated food products are ingested, especially uncooked or insufficiently cooked so-called "seafood", which often appear as gastronomic specialities in developed countries of Europe, Asia and America. India ranks first in terms of the number of infections. Growing clinical significance is currently also attributed to *V. vulnificus*, which causes gastroenteritis, skin infections, wound infections, and soft tissue infections.

As in previous years, no cases of cholera were reported in 2024. There was one case of middle ear infection and one case of wound infection caused by *V. alginolyticus*, and in two cases there was middle ear infection with the presence of *V. mimicus*. Of the four rectal swab samples, one case was reported with the presence of *V. furnissii* and one case with *V. cholerae* non-O1/non-O139. No diarrhoeal diseases were caused by *Vibrio* spp.

A total of 91 samples of various foodstuffs were examined. Different types of vibrios were isolated in several samples. Various types of vibrios were detected in surface waters used for bathing, especially from overheated waters in the summer season. The presence of *V. cholerae* non-O1/non-O139 and *V. alginolyticus* is significant. *V. fluvialis* is also regularly detected in waters in Slovakia, as these are pathogens from seaside areas, and they probably appear in our country in connection with climate warming.

9. *Aeromonas* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Aeromonas* (A.) grow in both aerobic and anaerobic conditions, in a temperature range from 0°C to 45°C, and live in wastewater, soil, and residual organic material. They can also survive in chlorinated drinking water or colonise the intestinal tracts of various animals. The *Aeromonas* genus is considered a serious aetiological agent of human infections, especially for those with compromised immune systems. They cause disease by releasing a cytotoxic enterotoxin and through surface adhesion and invasion. Disease caused by aeromonads can occur as a gastrointestinal or extraintestinal infection. The incubation period of gastrointestinal infections is one to two days. Sources of infection include water, soil, food, domestic and wild animals, and cold-blooded animals.

In 2024, 18 isolates from the stool of patients with severe diarrhoeal disease and four isolates from rectal swabs were sent to the National Reference Centre for Vibrionaceae for reidentification. Aeromonads were confirmed in 20 cases (16x *A. caviae*, 1x *A. hydrophila*, 1x *A. salmonicida*, 1x *A. media*, and 1x *A. popoffii*). Other aeromonads were reidentified 1x *A. hydrophila* (throat swab), 3x *A. caviae* (sputum, ejaculate, vaginal swab).

There were 78 strains isolated from the waters, most frequently identified as *A. bestiarum* 15x, *A. popoffii* 12x, and *A. hydrophila* 9x. Aeromonads were isolated from environmental samples in 42 cases, of which 5 strains were identified as *A. caviae* and 37 strains as *Aeromonas* spp.

The Regional Public Health Authority based in Prešov isolated a total of 50 aeromonads from the environment (14x *Aeromonas* spp.) – other waters, 34x *Aeromonas* spp. – environmental swabs and 2x *A. hydrophila* – other waters.) and the Veterinary and Food Institute in Dolný Kubín isolated 2 strains (other waters) of *A. hydrophila* and *A. caviae*.

10. *Campylobacter* spp.

The genus *Campylobacter* is an aetiological agent of intestinal infections in humans and an agent of abortions in livestock. Campylobacters are widespread in nature; their reservoir is the digestive tract of domestic and wild animals. The route of transmission can be faecal-oral, inter-human, sexual, and by consumption of contaminated food and water. The infectious dose is relatively low. The incubation time varies from two to five days. Among the most common clinical symptoms are diarrhoea, abdominal pain, fever, headache and muscle pain and also possible vomiting. After recovering from acute enteritis, patients may develop neurological disorders. Campylobacteriosis has been the most reported gastrointestinal disease in the EU since 2005, and since 2011 also in Slovakia. The average morbidity rate in 2023 in EU countries was 45.7/100,000 inhabitants, representing an increase of 4.3% compared to the reporting rate in 2022, with *C. jejuni* (87.3%) and *C. coli* (11%) contributing the most to this increase. The highest morbidity rates within the EU were in Luxembourg, the Czech Republic, Slovakia, and Malta, while the lowest rates were in Bulgaria, Greece, Poland, and Romania. There were 229 outbreaks reported in EU countries. The most common factor in the transmission of epidemics was broiler meat and its products.

In 2024, there were 6,511 cases of campylobacteriosis, with the highest incidence in the Prešov and Košice regions. There were 73 imported diseases and two major epidemics, with seven and eight cases reported, as well as 49 minor epidemics with two to four cases. The greatest contribution to diseases and epidemics was made by *C. jejuni*.

**Incidence of campylobacteriosis (A04.5).
20-year trend
2024, SR.**

Data source: EPIS. © ÚVZ SR

Fig. 2 Incidence of campylobacteriosis in Slovakia – 20-year trend, 2024

In 2024, out of 299 food samples of predominantly animal origin, 144 of which (broiler meat – fresh carcasses) were positive, the presence of *C. jejuni* (3) and *C. coli* (5) was confirmed in eight samples of broiler meat – fresh, and the presence of *C. coli* was confirmed in 5 samples of frozen poultry meat. Positive findings in foodstuffs as a whole accounted for 52.5%.

In 2024, 1,491 animal samples were tested for the presence of *Campylobacter* spp., of which 262 were positive, representing approximately 17.6% positivity. Nearly 73% of positive samples were from poultry (*Gallus gallus*).

Whole genome sequencing was compared with the results of a qualitative method of ATB sensitivity in order to examine the population structure and genetic mechanisms of virulence and AMR, confirming the increasing prevalence of resistance to fluoroquinolones and tetracyclines associated with the *gyrA* mutation and the *tet (O)* gene.

11. *Brucella* spp.

Bacteria from the *Brucella* genus are the cause of the zoonotic disease brucellosis. The source of infection is an infected animal or in rare cases a human, and it is transmitted through direct contact with the infectious animal, contaminated food, or an inhaled aerosol. The alimentary route of infection is most often through meat, raw milk, and its products. After penetrating the skin, mucous membranes, or digestive tract, the *Brucella* bacteria multiply in the lymph nodes and then attack other organs through the blood circulation. The pathogenicity of these bacteria is determined by endotoxins. Clinical course is acute and chronic. It has a wide range of manifestations, from a flu-like pattern, alternating periods with fever with periods without fever, causing damage to various parenchymatous organs (liver, spleen, gonads, heart, lungs) and rarely causing meningitis, encephalitis, neuritis, and myelitis. It causes miscarriages in pregnant women. Until 1960, a high incidence of disease occurred among cattle breeders, milkmaids, zootechnicians, and other professions involved in livestock production. In 2023, there were 259 cases of brucellosis in humans, which represents a relative increase of 14.1% compared to the previous year. Most reported infections were caused by *Brucella melitensis* bacteria. In 2023, no foodborne epidemics were reported. In 2023, 22 EU Member States and

the United Kingdom (Northern Ireland) had the status of a bovine brucellosis-free country. However, brucellosis remains a problem, particularly in southern Europe and the Balkans, where the presence of this disease persists.

While in the last 10 years, up to 2020, a maximum of one case per year was reported in Slovakia, in 2020 there were seven cases, in 2021 there were six cases, in 2022 there were three cases, and subsequently in 2023 there were 10 cases. During 2024, nine cases were reported: four in the Banská Bystrica Region, two in the Prešov Region, one in the Trenčín Region, one in the Nitra Region, and one in the Košice Region.

Slovakia is officially declared as a bovine, ovine and caprine brucellosis-free country. In order to maintain this level of status, 54,225 bovine serological tests and 11,212 ovine and caprine serological tests were carried out.

12. *Anaplasma phagocytophilum*

Anaplasma phagocytophilum is a bacteria of the order *Rickettsiales*, family *Anaplasmataceae*, which is the aetiological agent of human and animal granulocytic anaplasmosis. The primary European vector is the tick *Ixodes ricinus*. It attacks granulocytes in the host's blood and weakens the immune system. The incubation period is one to three weeks from the tick bite. The most common manifestation of infection is a non-specific flu-like illness with headache, muscle aches, sweating, weakness, and fever. It can be a threat especially for chronically ill patients. In animals, it causes granulocytic anaplasmosis of dogs, horses, and in ruminants it causes tick-borne fever. The most common sources of infection are rodents, deer, roe deer, foxes, cattle, sheep, horses, dogs, and other animals.

In 2024, *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* was confirmed in humans (especially in eastern Slovakia), in ticks collected from vegetation and in ticks collected from humans and dogs. It was not detected in blood samples from dogs. The highest prevalence in ticks was found in the locality of Cemjata (40%) Prešov. In humans the overall prevalence of tick-borne diseases was 7.6%.

In 2024, the Veterinary and Food Authority in Dolný Kubín examined 33 samples of blood serum and whole blood from dogs and horses. Of the dog samples tested, two were positive and four were suspected after blood swab testing. Horse samples were screened using an ELISA test with negative results. In 2024, the Parasitological Institute of the Slovak Academy of Sciences examined a total of 22 DNA samples from the blood of dogs, mainly from eastern Slovakia. The bacteria was not confirmed in any of the samples.

13. *Coxiella burnetii*

The intracellular bacterium *Coxiella burnetii* is the aetiological agent of the zoonotic disease Q fever. It is characterized by high resistance to physical and chemical agents and the ability to survive in the environment for a long time. Its natural reservoirs are various species of domestic and wild animals. Although infection in animals does not usually lead to obvious clinical signs, in cattle, goats, and sheep it may be associated with spontaneous abortions. The main source of infection in humans are ruminants. Infection most commonly occurs through inhalation of contaminated aerosol or dust, contact with infected animals, and consumption of contaminated milk. The incubation period of this disease is 20 days, but only 40% of infected humans have clinical symptoms. The acute form of Q fever manifests itself with high fever, headaches, fatigue, and tremors. In approximately 2% of cases, the disease may have a fatal course. Less common is a chronic form that is associated with complications such as endocarditis or liver disorders. The largest Q fever epidemic in Europe was recorded in the Netherlands between 2007 and 2010, with more than 4,000 confirmed cases. After an increase in incidence between 2012 and 2016, no significant upward or downward trend was observed between 2018 and 2023. A significant upward trend has been noticed in Hungary. In 2022, four deaths of people aged 35 – 70 were reported in Portugal and Spain.

In animals within the EU, the seroprevalence was reported in sheep, goats, and cattle in 2022. In other domestic and wild animals, positive results were reported only in Italy.

Since the 1993 epidemic, only occasional cases of this disease have occurred in Slovakia.

During 2024, three cases of the disease were reported (a morbidity rate of 0.06/100 000); in 2023, four cases were reported, and in 2022, not a single case was reported. The Virology Institute, Biomedical Centre of the Slovak Academy of Sciences has tested serum samples from 189 patients. The presence of antibodies against *Coxiella burnetii* phase II did not confirm the presence of acute or past Q fever.

A total of 839 samples from cattle, goats, and sheep were tested. Positive serological findings were found only in cattle – 1.45%. In the recent period, positive serological findings were seen in goats only in 2010 and 2013, and in the long term there have been no serological positive findings in sheep.

14. *Francisella tularensis*

The aetiological agent of tularaemia, a zoonosis with outbreaks in nature, is *Francisella (F.) tularensis*, a small, facultatively intracellular gram-negative bacterium. At its outbreak sites in nature, this pathogen circulates among various species of reservoir animals. Transmission can occur through both direct and indirect contact with an infected animal, inhalation of contaminated dust, aerosol, ingestion of undercooked products from infected animals, contaminated water, food, ticks, and stinging insects. The disease has a variable clinical picture; its symptoms include fever, headache, aching muscles and joints, and other symptoms. The incubation period of tularaemia is 3 – 8 days. Overcoming the disease results in long-term immunity.

According to the latest available EU One Health Zoonosis Report 2023, published in 2024, where summarising data for 2023 is published, a total of 1,185 human cases of tularaemia were confirmed across EU countries, which represents an incidence of 0.27 per 100,000 inhabitants. This represents an 89.3% increase compared to 2022, when the incidence was 0.14 per 100,000 inhabitants. Tularaemia was reported in a total of 25 EU countries. The incidence was confirmed in 19 countries, while in six countries it was not confirmed. As in 2022, the highest incidence rates among EU countries were recorded in Finland, France, Germany, and Sweden, which represented 78.9% of all confirmed cases of tularaemia in the EU. Outside the EU, Switzerland reported a total of 109 cases, Norway 149 cases, and Liechtenstein one case of human infection. Iceland and the UK did not report a single case in 2023. In 2023, there was an increase in the number of tularaemia cases, with 55% of cases reported in Sweden. The incidence of *F. tularensis* in animals in 2023, reported on a voluntary basis by EU countries, was recorded in Austria, Finland, and Sweden (30 rabbits, 10 small rabbits, 4 dogs). Among countries outside the EU, tularaemia was confirmed in animals in Switzerland in three rabbits.

The incidence of tularaemia in humans in Slovakia has been declining over a long period, but in 2024 there was an increase in the number of cases. In 2024, a total of 10 cases were reported (a morbidity rate of (0.2/100,000 inhabitants) According to available data and conclusions from the ECDC and EFSA, there remains a high risk of acquiring an infection caused by *F. tularensis* particularly in connection with contact with wild animals, domestic animals, and infected ticks. Therefore, monitoring at the vector level is also a very important tool for tularaemia surveillance. Cross-sector communication is essential, as this is the only way to ensure the surveillance of tularaemia and also prevent the outbreak of local epidemics. In Slovakia, cases were reported from the Nitra, Košice, Prešov, Bratislava and Banská Bystrica regions. These cases were spread across the age categories of 20 to 24 years, 25 to 34 years, 44 to 45 years, 45 to 64 years, and over 65 years. In the epidemiological history, four contacts with wild animals and one contact with a domestic animal were reported; in the remaining cases, the route of transmission was not clarified.

In 2024, veterinary services did not report any outbreak of hare tularaemia.

The results of the surveillance indicate the persistence of tularaemia outbreaks in nature, with circulating *F. tularensis* in the endemic area of western Slovakia and the possibility of exposure with the risk of acquiring the infection by different transmission mechanisms also outside the endemic areas. In view of this fact, the Information Centre for Bacteriological (Biological) and Toxin Warfare, which is established at the Regional Public Health Authority in Banská Bystrica, has started to investigate tularaemia in ticks. Cooperation has been established with the Institute of Virology of the BMC SAV, and the results will continue to be included in reports on zoonoses and will be presented at domestic and international platforms.

15. *Leptospira* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Leptospira* are spiral-shaped Gram-negative bacteria that cause the zoonotic disease of leptospirosis. Leptospirosis is a zoonosis primarily affecting wild and farm animals. The most important reservoirs are rodents, cattle, and pigs. In animals, the infection is usually asymptomatic, but clinically it can manifest itself in abortions or sterility in cattle and pigs. Infected animals, by virtue of leptospire persisting in the renal tubules, excrete these agents in the urine for months or years. Human infection occurs as a result of direct contact with an infected animal; more often it occurs indirectly, for example, through water and wet soil contaminated with the urine of the infected animals. Leptospiroses are a group of acute infectious diseases with a broad clinical picture; they may manifest as life-threatening hepatitis, meningitis, an influenza-like illness or as an inapparent infection. The disease may be accompanied by symptoms such as fever, malaise, headache, muscle aches, diarrhoea or cough, or more severe manifestations, such as pulmonary haemorrhage to respiratory failure, hepato-renal syndrome with haemorrhages or myocarditis. A severe form of the disease may result in death. Leptospirosis is a global problem, with regional differences observed due to varying natural and social factors. Populations in developing countries are most at risk because of lower social and hygiene standards and because of the warm and humid climate suitable for leptospire to survive outside the host organism.

In 2024, no foodborne epidemics were reported. Neighbouring countries also report low incidence rates. In general, a decline in leptospirosis cases has been observed in many European countries in the second half of the 20th century.

A total of 4,036 animal blood samples were tested, 2.4% of which were positive. Positive findings were reported in cattle, pigs, sheep, horses, dogs, and cats. The highest percentages of positivity were found in horses (37.5%) and sheep (33.3%), but only a small number of animals were tested, and some of them had a history of health problems.

16. *Borrelia* spp.

Bacteria of the genus *Borrelia* are composed of spirochetes that cause diseases in humans and animals. Depending on the disease and vector, they are classified into three evolutionary groups. Bacteria in the first group causes relapsing fever, and they are transmitted by soft ticks or lice. The disease is manifested by chills, headache, fever, myalgias, photophobia, and cough. Another group is made up of species of the complex *Borrelia burgdorferi* sensu lato, the aetiological agent of Lyme borreliosis. The vectors of this group are hard ticks. This zoonoanthroposis is manifested by multi-systemic impairment with a wide variability of clinical symptoms. The disease may progress as an early localised stage with the development of skin changes – erythema migrans – and with clinical symptoms similar to those of a viral infection. The third group in the *Borrelia* genus consists of bacteria species which are phylogenetically close to those in the first group, but which are transmitted by hard ticks. The disease symptoms are fever, fatigue, joint aches and neurological symptoms.

In 2024, 2,419 cases were reported in Slovakia, which is up by 20% compared to 2023. The disease is on the rise. Cases were reported from all regions, with the highest incidence in the Trenčín Region. The most common cause reported in the epidemiology history is tick

bites. In these cases, laboratory tests confirmed the presence of *Borrelia burgdorferi*, *Borrelia afzelii*, *Borrelia garinii* and *Borrelia species*.

Incidence of Lyme borreliosis (A69.2, M01.2, G63.0). 10-year trend 2024, SR.

Data source: EPIS. © ÚVZ SR

Fig. 3 The 10-year trend of Lyme borreliosis in Slovakia

During 2024, 18 blood serum samples from dogs from different regions of Slovakia were tested in the laboratory at the Veterinary and Food Institute in Dolný Kubín. Among the samples examined, IgM antibodies were detected in two blood sera (positive finding).

In 2024, the Virology Institute of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, using the RT-PCR method, examined 92 ticks that had fed on humans, and 28.3% of them tested positive for *Borrelia* DNA, which is comparable to the positivity rate in 2020 (27.2%).

During 2024, the Department of Epizootiology, Parasitology, and Public Health (UVLF Košice) examined using the PCR method 2,327 ticks collected from vegetation for the presence of *Borrelia* spp., of which 741 (31.84%) were positive.

17. Chlamydia

Chlamydiae, which have a cosmopolitan geographical distribution, are among the most widespread microorganisms in nature. For humans, *Chlamydia trachomatis* and *Chlamydia pneumoniae* – both primarily human pathogens – and *Chlamydia psittaci*, *Chlamydia abortus* and *Chlamydia felis* – primarily animal pathogens with a potential for transmission to humans (so-called anthrozooses) – are the most important in terms of potential disease contraction. Of the zoonotic species, *Chlamydia psittaci* poses the greatest risk to humans, occurring in approximately 460 different bird species, with nine known genotypes, all of which are zoonotic and can be transmitted to humans, in whom they cause ornithosis-psittacosis. Psittacosis refers to a disease that occurs when humans are infected by parrots; ornithosis refers to transmission from other bird species, including poultry. Transmission occurs via inhalation of an infectious aerosol or by direct contact with an infected individual. *Chlamydia psittaci* primarily causes respiratory infections in humans with variable clinical symptoms. Another species of chlamydia that is zoonotic is *Chlamydia abortus*. When transmitted to humans,

it poses a particular danger to pregnant women who have been in contact with sheep and other livestock. It may cause serious clinical conditions in them, including foetal miscarriage, pelvic inflammatory disease and impaired kidney function. In view of evidence and the differential diagnosis, all chlamydial infections represent a serious medical problem. Most of them do not have “typical” clinical symptoms that would allow the diagnostics to indicate the disease.

In 2024, one case of ornithosis-psittacosis was reported in humans (a morbidity rate of 0.02/100,000). This follows the trend from previous years, when, except for 2013, 2015, and 2024, no cases were reported in humans. The probable cause is the lack of differential laboratory diagnosis, as a result of which these infections may pass under a different diagnosis.

In animals, four blood serum samples from cats were tested for the presence of chlamydial antibodies in 2024, with a positive result confirmed in one case. For the first time, no other animal species were examined. Although testing for confirmation of chlamydiosis in animals has become optional and is not included in the Veterinary Prevention and Protection Plan for the Territory of the Slovak Republic, it should be noted that ruminants with reproductive problems and after miscarriage (especially sheep) have been serologically examined, as in previous years. This is also suggested by the fact that between 2019 and 2022, a relatively high average seropositivity was observed in this group of animals (approx. 17%). It is therefore desirable that animals (cattle, sheep, and goats) are examined regularly if abortions occur. Serological tests to prove specific antibodies and, above all, monitoring their dynamics in order to determine the aetiology of reproductive disorders and other health problems should be performed in a targeted manner. Animals should also be tested for chlamydiosis before their trade, sale, transfer and in quarantines.

18. *Mycobacterium* spp.

Pathogenic species from the genus *Mycobacterium* are the aetiological agents of tuberculosis in humans and animals. Zoonotic potential comes mainly from the *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex. Bacteria from a sick person or animal can be transmitted through the respiratory tract, contaminated food, direct contact with wounded skin, or through the mucous membranes. The risk of infection depends on several factors, such as: the infectivity of the source, the closeness of contact, the quantity of bacteria inhaled, and the condition of the host’s immune system. Clinical signs include weakness, fatigue, lack of appetite, loss of weight, subfebrility, night sweats, muscle and joint ache, cough, later manifested by cyanosis, dyspnoea, and chest pain. Tuberculosis remains one of the deadliest infectious killers in the world. Every day, nearly 3,425 people die from tuberculosis and nearly 30,000 people contract this preventable and treatable disease. Global efforts to combat tuberculosis have saved an estimated 79 million lives since 2000. In 2025, rapid diagnostic tests are expected to improve, enabling tuberculosis to be identified in its early stages, which will facilitate its rapid treatment. New diagnostic methods, such as advanced genetic testing or artificial intelligence, can increase the efficiency of diagnostics in the field.

The development of a new tuberculosis vaccine is a key step in the fight against this serious infection, which affects approximately 10.8 million people each year and causes more than 1.25 million deaths. Currently, the most widely used vaccine against TB is the BCG vaccine (*Bacillus Calmette-Guérin*), which was developed more than 100 years ago. Although it provides protection against severe forms of TB in children, its effectiveness in adults is limited. Therefore, the development of new, more effective vaccines is essential.

Tuberculosis eradication is an ambitious goal that requires coordinated global efforts. Complete eradication is difficult due to the long incubation period, the need for long-term treatment, and the emergence of resistant strains. However, with advances in diagnostics, the development of new drugs and vaccines, improved access to healthcare, and global cooperation, it is possible to achieve a significant reduction in the incidence of tuberculosis and its eventual elimination in some regions.

Currently, the situation in Slovakia is stable. In 2024, 135 cases were reported to the National Tuberculosis Register in Vyšné Hágy. According to the geographical distribution in the Slovak Republic, the worst areas with the highest incidence of this disease are in eastern Slovakia (Prešov Region and Košice Region). In third place is the Bratislava Region – due mainly to foreigners and homeless people.

Also in 2024, the Slovak Republic retained its status as an officially bovine tuberculosis-free country. In 2024, no samples from animals were tested for suspicion of tuberculosis at the Research institute based in Zvolen.

Situation with TB disease in Slovakia.

Source: NRT

Fig. 4 Overview of the situation with TB disease in Slovakia during the

19. *Listeria* spp.

Of the *Listeriae* currently known, *Listeria monocytogenes* is the only pathogenic species and the causative agent of the zoonotic disease listeriosis, which is characterised by high mortality. *Listeria* are capable of reproducing themselves even during food storage in the refrigerator and are resistant to higher concentrations of cooking salt. A reservoir of *Listeria* in the wild are rodents. The most common mode of transmission to humans is the consumption of contaminated food, especially raw or uncooked food. The disease is manifested by flu-like symptoms, including fever, muscle aches, and gastrointestinal discomfort. Due to the prolonged incubation period, it is often very difficult to determine the source of infection. In 2023, a total of 335 deaths were reported as being caused by *L. monocytogenes*. The highest incidence of outbreaks was reported in Germany and Denmark. In 2023, there were 19 reported food-borne listeriosis outbreaks in the EU, in which 133 people fell ill; among food products, pork and fish products were the main contributors to the epidemics.

In 2024, a total of 14 cases of listeriosis were reported in Slovakia, which is a decline of 33% compared to 2023 and 18% compared to the five-year average. In 2024, no cases of neonatal (disseminated) listeriosis were reported, while in the previous year, one case was registered.

Most cases were reported from the Bratislava and Prešov regions. Cases were reported in the age groups of 5 to 9 years and over 35 years. In one case, the death of a woman in the age group over 65 years from the Bratislava Region was reported.

In 2024, 8,980 samples from 31 types of food were tested. The positivity rate was 0.84%. Higher percentages of positive findings were reported in raw cow's milk and raw meat.

In 2024, 80 samples from 8 animal species were tested. A positive finding for the presence of *L. monocytogenes* was detected in cattle, sheep, and goats. A positive finding for the presence of *Listeria* spp. was detected in a brown hare.

In 2024, as in previous years, serotype 1/2a was the most frequently isolated serotype from food, accounting for 66.7%.

20. *Bacillus anthracis*

Bacteria of the species *Bacillus anthracis* are the aetiological agent of splenic anthrax, which is primarily a disease of ruminants but may also affect all mammals, including humans. Anthrax spores can survive in the environment for more than 100 years, making contaminated soil or animal raw materials a permanent source of infection. The human disease varies according to the site of infection and has three main forms – skin, gastrointestinal, and pulmonary. Anthrax is a rare disease in EU countries. In 2017 – 2021, EU/EEA countries reported 17 confirmed cases, from one to six per year. In 2021, four confirmed cases of anthrax were reported, in Bulgaria (one case) and in Spain (three cases). Three probable cases were reported – in France (one case) and Spain (two cases). Among 30 EU/EEA reporting countries, 27 reported zero cases. In June 2022, 100 cattle died from anthrax in Croatia, and six people became infected. According to the latest available EU One Health Zoonoses Report from 2024, which summarises data for 2023, 15 animals (cattle, goats, sheep, and pigs) were tested in Greece. In one case, cattle tested positive, and in another case, the disease was confirmed in a goat.

The last case of anthrax in humans in Slovakia was reported in 2003 and in animals in 2014.

Also 19 samples from the leather industry were tested with negative results and none of the 6 samples from the suspicious shipments showed *B. anthracis* spores.

As part of improving preparedness for the possible misuse of *B. anthracis* as a biological weapon, or the investigation of threatening parcels, several educational activities took place in 2024 in which employees of the Information Centre for Bacteriological (Biological) and Toxin Weapons participated: the Triglav Project – strengthening the fight against CBRN threats on the Ukrainian-Slovak border; a regional training course for BWC (Biological Weapons Convention) National contact points, and a Global Workshop for BWC National contact points (both in Geneva, Switzerland).

21. *Clostridioides* spp.

The bacterial genus *Clostridium* (*Cl.*) causes various types of disease in humans and animals. The basis of its pathogenicity is the production of exotoxins. *Cl. botulinum* is the aetiological agent of botulism in humans and animals. Infection is manifested by dry mouth; paralysis of the eyes, skeletal and respiratory muscles; and a swallowing and speech disorder. Death comes on the 2nd to 5th day after ingestion; the mortality rate is 17 – 80%. In the past, the risks of alimentary botulism were associated with home-canned food, but nowadays industrially produced food or food prepared in restaurants has become of increasing epidemiological importance. In 2023, there were 112 cases of botulism in 12 EU countries, with as many as 36 in Italy. *Cl. perfringens* is a common cause of food poisoning. The incubation period is 6 – 24 hours. The disease symptoms are cramps, diarrhoea, and sometimes fever and vomiting. In animals, especially young ones, *Cl. Perfringens* causes intestinal diseases. Another group are wound infections caused by several types of clostridia – *Cl. perfringens*, *Cl. septicum*, *Cl. histolyticum*, *Cl. Novyi*, *Cl. sordelli* as well as *Cl. tetani*.

In 2024, one case caused by *Cl. botulinum* (A05.1) was reported; no cases were reported last year. During 2024, a total of 4,846 cases of *Cl. difficile* (A04.7) were reported, which is a 3% increase compared to 2023 (when 4,716 cases were reported) and a 10% increase compared to the five-year average. Cases of A 04.7 were reported from all regions of Slovakia, with the highest incidence in the Žilina, Prešov, and Banská Bystrica regions and the lowest incidence in the Trnava Region. A total of 2,416 food samples were tested for *Cl. perfringens*, of which only 0.12% were positive. Out of 2,368 food samples tested for *sulphite-reducingclostridia* only 0.12% of samples were found positive. A total of 1,459 samples from clinically sick or dead animals were tested for *Clostridioides* spp., and 65.2% were found to be positive. Out of the 103 feed samples tested for *Clostridioides* spp., 12.6% were found to be positive, mainly in hay, haylage, and silage. The bacteria *Cl. perfringens* is an indicator parameter for faecal water pollution, and 987 water samples were tested for its presence. None of the bottled, spring, or mineral water samples tested were positive; positive findings were detected in drinking water. In total, 199 water samples were tested for *sulphite-reducing clostridia*, with positive findings in 40.7% of them; all positive findings were in surface water samples only, where from 98% of samples tested, 82.6% were found positive.

22. *Staphylococcus aureus* (coagulase-positive staphylococci and their toxins)

Staphylococcus aureus is a gram-positive coccus, a bacterium that is found in more than 50% of healthy humans. In addition to being an aetiological agent itself, it is also characterised by its ability to produce toxins. Following the consumption of food containing these toxins, food poisoning is developed – staphylococcal enterotoxigenesis. Humans are the most sensitive to their effect. The source of the disease may be all kinds of contaminated food, especially food protein-rich ready-to-eat dairy products, filled confectionery and bakery and delicatessen products. The risk of disease from staphylococcus-contaminated food increases with time, inappropriate food storage temperature, and conditions inside the food. In 2023, there were 207 epidemics in European Union countries caused by toxins produced by *Staphylococcus aureus*.

In 2024, there were 17 gastroenteritis cases caused by *Staphylococcus aureus*, all occurring within a single epidemic.

A total of 9,752 food samples were tested for coagulase-positive staphylococci, of which 0.91% exceeded the specified limits. Higher percentages of samples exceeding the limit were found in breast milk (4.73%), milk and dairy products (6.58%), and fishery products (6.06%). Staphylococcal enterotoxin was detected in five samples from the milk and dairy products group. Enterotoxin production was evidenced in 17 isolates (27.89%) from ready-to-eat meals, breast milk, fish products, delicatessen products, and frozen creams and ice creams. Biological material from animals was examined in clinically ill animals, where the positive detection rate of *S. aureus* in 2,711 samples was 10.33% cases.

Out of 31,354 samples of water and environmental swabs, *S. aureus* was detected in 1.27% of cases, with the largest number of positive swabs coming from hospitals. Toxin-producing isolates were also found mainly in swabs from a hospital environment and food processing facilities.

Antimicrobial resistance was monitored in 186 samples of food, animals, water, and the environment, and resistance was observed in 3.23% of the samples. In food, 5.55% of isolates tested positive for methicillin-resistant *S. aureus*, and 44 samples from various animals tested positive for methicillin-resistant *S. aureus* 9.09% of isolates. Resistance to methicillin was observed in 124 isolates from water and the environment, and 0.81% of the isolates were found resistant; isolates from water did not show resistance.

23. *Enterococcus* spp.

Enterococcus spp. is a genus of gram-positive cocci, characterised by high resistance, containing more than 50 species, many of which belong to the normal gut microbiota of humans

and animals, but some are aetiological agents of human disease. Most often they cause infections of the urogenital tract, bacteraemia, endocarditis, diverticulitis, soft tissue infections of the pelvic area, and postoperative wounds. Due to their natural and acquired resistance to antibiotics, enterococci are important nosocomial pathogens. The development and rapid spread of vancomycin-resistant enterococci is currently considered a significant global threat. While *E. faecalis* is the more frequently detected species, *Enterococcus faecium* is more problematic because of its resistance, especially to vancomycin. In veterinary medicine, this trend is not yet as pronounced as in human medicine, but the incidence of urinary tract infections caused by enterococci is increasing. The presence of enterococci in water is one of the indicators of faecal contamination.

In 2024, two cases caused by *Enterococcus faecalis* were reported and were of a nosocomial pattern.

Out of 10 food samples, 30% were positive. Out of 18,529 water samples, 6.4% were above the regulatory limit or tested positive. Out of 29,036 environmental samples, *Enterococcus* spp. were detected in 2.2% of them, with most samples tested positive coming from fertilisers and secondary nutrient sources (digestate, fugate). Out of 731 animal samples, enterococci were found in all the tested birds, with an overall percentage of positive samples was 3.7%. Antibiotic-resistant enterococci were present in six samples of surface water used for swimming. The prevalent resistance was to ampicillin, gentamicin, and vancomycin.

24. Lyssavirus

The agents of rabies are RNA viruses of the genus *Lyssavirus*. This disease affects all types of warm-blooded animals and is transmissible to humans. The virus is excreted by the saliva of infected animals. Upon penetration into the organism, it spreads to the central nervous system, where it multiplies and causes inflammation of the brain; later it spreads through nerve fibres from the brain to the salivary glands and saliva. The incubation period is 1 to 3 months. The first stage of rabies is excitatory, manifested by inappropriate behaviour, disorientation, hallucinations, and painful convulsions. The second stage is paralytic, manifested by paralysis, mainly of the cranial nerves. Among animals, foxes are particularly susceptible to rabies. After the onset of rabies, the mortality rate is 100%. Protective vaccination is the only effective measure.

The last rabies disease in humans in Slovakia was reported in 1990. In 2024, 900 cases of rabies threats were reported after people came into contact with animals that were or were suspected of being rabid (a morbidity rate of 16.59/100,000), which is up by 18% compared to last year and represents a 51% increase compared to the five-year average. Cases of rabies were reported from all regions of Slovakia, with the highest incidence in the Banská Bystrica Region.

In 2024, 927 animals were tested for rabies virus at the National Reference Laboratory, and one sample was positive (red fox, Michalovce). As part of the eradication programme, 735,592 vaccination doses were laid for the oral vaccination of foxes.

25. Influenza virus

Influenza is among the oldest infectious and transmissible diseases of humans and animals; it is caused by an RNA virus. Originally, it was exclusively an infection of water birds, but over the centuries it has adapted to several mammals, including humans. The most dangerous are type A influenza viruses, which infect humans, several species of mammals, and a wide variety of birds. The genus *Influenza virus A*, including avian influenza viruses, which are carried by water birds. The infection causes a wide spectrum of symptoms in birds, from a mild course to a highly contagious and rapidly fatal disease. This form is also known as HPAI – *highly pathogenic avian influenza*. It is characterised by rapid onset, a severe course of the disease, and rapid death, with mortality approaching 100%. Infected birds shed the virus in nasal secretions, saliva, and faeces.

In 2024, 219,098 cases of influenza and influenza-like illnesses were reported, with a morbidity rate of 9,039.4/100,000 inhabitants in the care of reporting physicians. The highest incidence of influenza and influenza-like illnesses was reported in the Trnava Region (16,212.4/100,000). Age-specific morbidity was the highest in the group 0 to 5-year-olds and the lowest in the group over 60. In samples positive for influenza, the influenza A virus was prevalent over the influenza B virus.

The Research institute in Zvolen tested 950 blood samples from 101 poultry farming holdings without any positive findings. A total of 106 samples from wild birds and 916 samples from domestic poultry were tested using the avian influenza virus nucleic acid detection method. A total of 75 samples tested positive.

26. Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBEV)

Tick-borne encephalitis (TBE) is a disease affecting humans and warm-blooded animals. There are three subtypes known, with the European subtype being associated with a milder disease course and a mortality rate of 0.5 – 2%, with almost 10% of patients subsequently suffering from various neurological problems. The incubation period is 7 – 28 days. The disease proceeds in several forms, such as: abortive, meningitic, encephalic, encephalomyelitic, and bulbo-cervical. The clinical course of the disease usually has two stages. The first phase resembles the flu and is followed by a symptom-free period lasting 1 – 20 days. Typical second-phase symptoms are headaches, photophobia, double vision, and vomiting. The animals serving as the virus reservoir for tick-borne encephalitis are rodents and insectivores, and ticks are the vector. Tick-borne encephalitis can also be transmitted via the alimentary route, for example, through milk from infected animals. The best form of protection is vaccination.

During 2024, a total of 172 cases were reported as A84.1 Central European tick-borne encephalitis (a morbidity rate of 3.17/100 000), which is a drop by 14% compared to last year and which is comparable to the five-year average. Only sporadic cases were reported, with no epidemic occurrence. The incidence was reported from all regions except the Trnava Region, with the highest incidence in the Banská Bystrica Region (a morbidity rate of 7.98/100,000) and the Žilina region (a morbidity rate of 7.71/100,000). Only sporadic cases were reported, with no epidemic occurrence.

In 2024, 179 samples of milk and milk products were tested for tick-borne encephalitis, all with a negative outcome. The Virology Institute of the BMC of the Slovak Academy of Sciences examined 27 ticks parasitizing on humans with one positive finding and 42 ticks from vegetation with negative results. The University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice analysed 2,372 ticks collected from plants for the presence of the tick-born encephalitis viruses, with no positive findings.

Incidence of tick-borne encephalitis (A84.0, A84.1, A84.8) in the SR, in 2024

Fig. 5 Incidence of tick-borne encephalitis by districts in Slovakia in 2024

27. West Nile virus (WNV)

West Nile virus (WNV) is a mosquito-borne arbovirus that causes West Nile fever. Birds are the reservoir and main host of the virus, while various types of mosquitoes that suck the infected blood of birds serve as vectors. WNV is transmitted through mosquito bites. Human infection can also occur through blood transfusions or organ or tissue transplants. Humans and horses are accidental hosts and do not contribute to further transmission. Both humans and other mammals may contract the infection, with approximately 80% of infections being asymptomatic. The mild form (known as West Nile fever) manifests itself as fever, headache, myalgia, rash, or fatigue. Currently, there is no human vaccine against the virus, nor is there any specific treatment; only supportive care is administered. The mortality rate is around 17%. In Europe, in 2024, there were 1,436 locally acquired human cases (91% hospitalised, 9% mortality), and 494 outbreaks in ungulates and 447 outbreaks in birds were reported. The peak of transmission traditionally occurred in August and September.

Since 2019, the first autochthonous human cases of West Nile fever have been reported in Slovakia. In 2024, nine cases of West Nile fever were reported, while in 2023 no cases were recorded. Three cases were imported – from Albania, Austria, and the United Arab Emirates.

All cases were laboratory confirmed, with three cases identified by sequencing as WNV L2.type.

Among the 43 animal samples tested (horses, birds), only one case tested positive for WNV – a Harris hawk from the Detva District. WNV was also confirmed in 7 pools of the mosquito *Culex pipiens* from four locations (the districts of Dunajská Streda, Komárno, Veľký Krtíš, Michalovce) and in mosquito saliva collected in the districts of Nové Zámky and Košice.

28. Dengue virus

Dengue fever is caused by a virus that infects humans and primates and is transmitted by mosquitoes of the species *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus*. The disease is widespread in Asia, the Pacific, and the Caribbean regions. In 1970, dengue fever was endemic in only nine countries outside Europe. In Europe, it has occurred only as a result of travel activities; however, in September 2012, the virus was introduced from South America to the island of Madeira, and in 2018, nine autochthonous cases of the disease were confirmed in the EU. The disease may have a febrile course, or it may appear as a haemorrhagic fever. Its incubation period is 3 to 14 days. In 2023, a total of 5,510 cases were reported in EU countries. The highest incidence was reported in France, Germany, and Spain. In 2024, France and Italy reported the highest incidence of dengue fever among EU/EEA countries.

In 2024, 10 imported cases of the disease were reported (a morbidity rate of 0.18/100,000), which is four cases more than in the previous year. The cases of the disease that occurred in the past were all imported infections.

29. Hantaviruses

Hantaviruses cause diseases belonging to the group of haemorrhagic fevers in humans, but they are not transmissible from person to person. Their reservoir is rodents that excrete the virus in urine, stool, and saliva. The most common mode of transmission to humans is inhalation of contaminated dust. Cases of hantavirus infection are more frequent in years in which rodents are overpopulated. In Europe, including Slovakia, the disease is caused by several types of hantaviruses. In 2023, 28 EU/EEA countries reported 1,885 cases of hantavirus infection. Two countries (Finland and Germany) accounted for 60.5% of all reported cases. Prevention relies mainly on rodent control, avoiding contact with rodent excrement (urine, saliva, or droppings), and disinfecting areas contaminated with rodent excrements.

In Slovakia, the incidence of haemorrhagic fever cases with hantavirus origin is on the rise. Surveillance of hantaviruses began to improve after the establishment of the NRC for hantaviruses and haemorrhagic fevers, where, since 2017, more cases have been reported. In 2024, a total of 75 cases were reported (a morbidity rate of 1.38/100,000), which is a 51% decrease compared to the previous year. Cases were reported in all age groups, with the highest morbidity in the group of 10 – 14 years old (a morbidity rate of 2.06/100,000). Cases were reported in all regions, with the highest morbidity reported in the Prešov, Košice and Žilina regions.

30. Norovirus

Norovirus is a virus from the *Caliciviridae*, family, which is one of the most common causes of viral gastroenteritis in humans. It causes sudden diarrhoea, vomiting, abdominal pain, and occasionally also fever. The illness is usually temporary, lasting 1 to 3 days, and does not leave any persistent health consequences. The norovirus got its name after the city of Norwalk in the US state of Ohio, where it was first identified in 1968 during an epidemic among schoolchildren. The older name “Norwalk virus” is now only used for the original reference strain (Norwalk virus GI.1). Norwalk virus, also known as the “winter vomiting virus”, is a small, highly contagious virus whose only reservoir is human beings. Transmission occurs

via the faecal-oral route, as well as contaminated food and drink. Its incubation period is 12 to 72 hours. In particular, uncooked foods pose a risk.

In 2024, 3,210 cases of norovirus infection were reported in Slovakia, representing an 11% year-on-year increase. The highest age-specific morbidity was reported in the age groups of 0 years and of 1 to 4 years. Out of the total number, 194 cases were of nosocomial nature. Noroviruses caused 54 epidemics, 26 of which were major epidemics. There were 11 imported cases, mostly from Croatia and Turkey. No deaths were reported.

One sample was tested for the presence of norovirus in food, with a negative result.

31. Rotavirus

The rotavirus is an RNA virus that mutates and recombines easily and that is stable and capable of rapid multiplication. It can survive in the air and on contaminated surfaces for several days. It is transmitted via the faecal-oral route, through consumption of contaminated food or contaminated objects. The incubation period of infection is one to three days. Early symptoms include fever, vomiting and abdominal pain. Children under the age of five are at high risk from the disease. Humans gradually develop immunity, and in adulthood, a more severe course occurs only when the immune system is generally weakened. In Europe, the disease is most common in the autumn and winter. The best form of protection against infection is vaccination.

In 2024, 4,516 cases of rotavirus intestinal disease were reported in Slovakia, representing a 33% decrease in morbidity. Cases were reported in all regions, with the highest incidence in the Prešov Region. The highest morbidity rate was among infants and children under 4 years of age. The diseases occurred sporadically, in families, and epidemically – a total of 47 epidemics, of which 9 were major. Out of the total number, 255 cases were of nosocomial nature. There were 38 imported cases, mostly from Croatia and Turkey. No deaths were reported.

Food and water were not tested for the presence of the virus.

32. Hepatitis A virus

Hepatitis A virus (HAV) is an RNA virus of the genus *Hepatovirus* family *Picornaviridae*. HAV is resistant to high temperatures, acids, and alkalis. Humans are the main reservoir of infection, which spreads via the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, and food. Seafood and vegetables fertilised with organic fertilisers pose an increased risk. HAV causes acute liver inflammation, with an incubation period of 15 to 50 days. HAV is one of the diseases that must be reported to the network for surveillance of contagious diseases in the EU. The latest processed data for the EU are available for 2023. This year, 6,199 cases were reported in EU countries, of which 1,905 cases were reported in Slovakia, which definitely had the highest incidence rate of 35.1/100,000. This was followed by Estonia, Romania, Bulgaria, and Malta. Besides Slovakia, the highest number of cases occurred in Germany, Romania, France, and Spain, but with a significantly lower incidence rate.

Since 2020, there has been a significant decline in HAV morbidity, probably as a result of preventive measures taken in connection with the COVID-19 pandemic – in particular, regular hand disinfection and restrictions on social contact. However, in 2023, there was a sharp increase, with 1,907 cases reported, representing a 30.1-fold increase compared to 2022. In 2024, 4,069 cases of HAV were reported in Slovakia, corresponding to an incidence rate of 75.01 per 100,000 inhabitants. This represents a 2.1-fold increase compared to 2023 and a 9.7-fold increase compared to the five-year average. In several locations in the Košice and Prešov regions, the incidence of disease had epidemic characteristics. One death was reported in a child of the age group of 10 – 14 years in the Poprad District.

In 2024, five strawberry samples were tested for the presence of hepatitis A virus, with negative results.

Incidence of the Hepatitis A-type (B15, B15.0) in the SR, in 2024

Fig. 6 Incidence of HAV by districts in Slovakia in 2024

33. Hepatitis E virus

Viral hepatitis E (HEV) is an infectious disease of the liver that spreads through the faecal-oral route, contaminated water, food, and transfusions. The most common route of HEV transmission is the consumption of raw or undercooked pork, venison, and liver, or products made from them. There are many known cases worldwide of VHE transmission through transfusion or transplantation. Its incubation period ranges from 14 to 70 days. Typical symptoms of acute illness are flu-like symptoms, joint pain, and gastrointestinal problems. Chronic course may result in chronic infection with fibrosis and liver cirrhosis. The WHO organizes World Hepatitis Day every year to raise awareness about viral hepatitis. At World Hepatitis Day 2023, the WHO focused on the topic “One Life, One Liver” to illustrate the importance of the liver for a healthy life and the need to scale up prevention, testing, and treatment of viral hepatitis to prevent liver disease, thus achieving the goal of hepatitis elimination by 2030.

Since 2012, HEV has showed an increasing trend in Slovakia. In 2024, 172 cases of the disease were reported in Slovakia, with the highest incidence in the Prešov and Košice regions. The highest age-specific morbidity was in the age group of 45 to 54 years. In seven cases, the infection was imported from Greece, the Netherlands, Indonesia, Iceland, the USA, Italy, and the United Kingdom. According to an analysis of clinical samples performed by UVLF in Košice, the genotyping of clinical samples of cases in Slovakia shows the occurrence of the genotype HEV-3, which is frequently found in Western European countries.

In 2024, the presence of HEV RNA was not confirmed in any food and animal samples analysed.

**Incidence of the selected diagnosis in the SR according to place of residence,
in 2024
Diagnosis B172**

Fig. 7 HEV incidence by districts in Slovakia in 2024

34. Enteroviruses

The most numerous family, *Picornaviridae*, also includes the genus *Enterovirus* (EV), which comprises 15 species. The genus *Enterovirus* represents a large group of small, globally widespread, non-enveloped RNA viruses with single-stranded nucleic acid of positive polarity. Enterovirus types of *Enterovirus* A-D and *Rhinovirus* A-C include medically important human pathogens, while to the types of *Enterovirus* E-L belong EVs that infect animals. The most important serotypes of this genus are polioviruses (PV) 1–3, whose occurrence in the world is strictly monitored by the WHO. Other enteroviruses, non-polio enteroviruses (NPEV), are amongst the most common human viral infections. The disease is mainly transmitted via the faecal-oral route (less often by infected aerosols), while it spreads more rapidly in closed communities (households, nurseries, hostels, shopping malls...). EV infections occur in higher incidence in late summer and early autumn. The virus is most often eliminated by the host's immune system in the early stages of infection, so the disease often runs its course inapparently or with only flu-like symptoms, and the body heals spontaneously. However, in some cases EV infections can have a serious, even fatal impact on the body. The severity of the disease is influenced by the patient's condition and the pathogenetic properties of the virus. The risk group includes newborns, children, the elderly, and immunocompromised people. Currently, due to the large global migration of the human population, surveillance of EVs is still an important part of PV control as part of their global eradication.

In 2024, the samples tested for enterovirus infection at NRC IEV were negative. The NRC for poliomyelitis confirmed enterovirus infection in 18 samples from 15 patients. In wastewater samples, EV was isolated in 34 samples.

In 2024, the PV was not isolated either in clinical samples or in wastewater samples.

In 2024, circulating vaccine-derived PV type 2 (cVDPV2) was reported in causal association with a case in the Gaza Strip (1 ACHO case) and 20 detections in wastewater samples. In the WHO Euroregion, cVDPV2 was isolated in wastewater samples in Spain once (Barcelona); Poland twice (Warsaw); Germany 22 times (Cologne, Bonn, Dresden, Düsseldorf, Mainz,

Hamburg, and Munich); Finland once (Tampere) and the United Kingdom six times (Leeds, London, and Worthing).

The detected virus is genetically linked to a strain that emerged in Nigeria and is circulating in several countries outside the region, most notably in North and West Africa, suggesting that it was brought to Europe by migrants.

Given the potential for global movement of travellers (including refugees and migrants) and the ongoing military conflict in Ukraine, where PV vaccination rates are below 50% in some regions, whereas in 2021 two cases of polio from Ukraine were reported and 19 contacts with polio virus infection, it is important that the EV surveillance system continues.

35. Prions

The cause of transmissible, incurable, and fatal prion-induced diseases in both humans and animals is the production of excessive amounts of prion protein and its subsequent transformation into a pathogenic form. The prions that cause bovine spongiform encephalopathy (BSE) are able to overcome the interspecies barrier and are transmitted to humans and different animal species. Humans have developed a new variant of Creutzfeldt-Jakob disease (vCJD) after consuming BSE-infected beef. It was transmitted from human to human through blood transfusions. Transmission to humans has not been proven in sheep and goat prion disease (scrapie). In addition to the classical form of scrapie, there is also an atypical form of scrapie that is detected in Slovakia.

In 2024, the incidence of CJD was laboratory confirmed in 24 cases, representing a morbidity of 0.44/100,000. The most cases were reported in the Žilina and Trenčín regions. The oldest patient was 82 and the youngest was 55.

In total, 6,113 samples from cattle were tested for BSE, all of which returned negative results. The last confirmed case of BSE in Slovakia was diagnosed in 2010. A total of 14,546 samples were taken from sheep and goats, which were tested for scrapie. One case of atypical scrapie in sheep was reported; all samples taken from goats were tested with negative results.

Currently, the situation regarding the incidence of BSE in Slovakia is very favourable. The scrapie situation in sheep and goats is under control, but in the coming years the occurrence of scrapie, especially the atypical form, must be expected in the sheep population.

36. *Toxoplasma gondii*

Toxoplasma (T.) gondii is an obligate intracellular parasite with a cosmopolitan distribution that is capable of infecting almost all species of warm-blooded animals. *T. gondii* is an important pathogen in terms of both human and veterinary medicine. The intermediate host, including humans, becomes infected by ingesting oocysts from contaminated fruits or vegetables, or by swallowing tissue cysts in raw or undercooked meat. The infection can also be transmitted transplacentally from mother to foetus, as well as through blood transfusions and transplanted organs. The disease often presents asymptotically. According to the latest scientific studies, about 20% of the human population in Slovakia is infected.

Toxoplasmosis has been on a downward trend since 2016. However, in 2024, there was a 53% increase in reported cases compared to 2023. Cases were reported from all regions and in all age groups. In 2024, no cases of congenital toxoplasmosis in newborns was reported.

Food was not tested for the presence of *Toxoplasma gondii*, and there is no legal obligation to do so, despite the fact that some meats pose a risk of contracting this parasite. Out of 1,902 samples of blood and faeces from animals tested by the State Veterinary and Food Administration and Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, 9.4% were positive.

37. *Plasmodium* spp.

Parasitic protozoa of the genus *Plasmodium* are the aetiological agents of malaria. Their vector of transmission and definitive hosts are mosquitoes of the genus *Anopheles*, six species of which are also found in Slovakia. The first symptoms are headache, muscle pain, and vomiting, followed by a malarial attack with chills, high fever, and convulsions. *Plasmodium falciparum* causes the most severe clinical forms of disease, including liver and kidney failure, encephalopathy, cerebral oedema, and coma. Malaria was endemic in European Union countries until the 1970s. It was eradicated in Slovakia in 1963. Around 99% of malaria cases reported each year in the EU are travel-related. In 2023, when comprehensive data for the EU was processed, a total of 7,172 cases were reported, with the highest incidence in France, Germany, and Spain. In all cases, these were imported infections.

In 2024, six cases were reported in Slovakia (a morbidity of 0.11/100,000); all cases were imported. In 2023, 9 imported cases were reported. These cases were from Tanzania (three cases), Nigeria (one case), Ivory Coast (one case), and Senegal (one case).

38. *Babesia* spp.

Intracellular coccidia of the genus *Babesia* are obligate unicellular parasites that attack erythrocytes and cells of the reticuloendothelial system of mammals and birds. More than 100 species of *Babesia* are known. They cause babesiosis, a disease with the character of natural focality. The natural reservoir are mostly small rodents. Although babesiosis is primarily an animal disease, cases of human babesiosis have been reported. Human infections usually follow tick infestation. However, in rare cases, the infection can also be transmitted through blood transfusions. The incubation period of the disease is one to six weeks, and the symptoms are similar to those of malaria, but without the periodicity symptom. The disease manifests itself through malaise, fatigue, chills, headaches, high temperatures, anaemia, anorexia, night sweats, weight loss, and haematuria.

In 2024, as in previous years, no human babesiosis was reported.

Out of the 37 animal blood samples tested, only samples from dogs and goats were found positive. It is likely that a large number of positive findings are not registered, as the veterinary clinics do not report their diagnoses or treat dogs only for their clinical symptoms.

39. *Echinococcus* spp.

Echinococcosis is a zoonotic parasitic disease caused by tapeworms of the *Echinococcus* genus. The definitive hosts of *Echinococcus granulosus* are dogs, wolves, and jackals. Intermediate hosts include domestic and wild ruminants, pigs, horses, and also humans. The definitive hosts of *Echinococcus multilocularis* are carnivores (in Slovakia, mainly the red fox), and its intermediate hosts are small mammals. Humans are accidental intermediate hosts in which the tapeworm cycle ends, with no possibility of further spread. Transmission occurs through parasite eggs, which humans become infected by contact with infected animals or contaminated food. Since 2012, the prevalence of *Echinococcus multilocularis* has also increased in foxes in south-western Slovakia, where its incidence until then was rare. In 2023, 929 cases of disease and 3 deaths caused by parasites of the genus *Echinococcus*, were reported in the EU, which represents an 8.4% increase compared to 2022. Infections caused by the type *Echinococcus granulosus* were observed mainly in sheep and goats and, to a lesser extent, in cattle and pigs. The highest incidence of definitive hosts (foxes) infected with *Echinococcus multilocularis* was reported in Poland and Czechia.

In 2024, 18 cases of echinococcosis in humans were reported in Slovakia, representing an increase of 8 cases compared to 2023. Etiologically, the dominant type was *E. multilocularis*. In 2024, 493,223 animals were tested for presence of echinococci. Apart from the positive findings of *Echinococcus granulosus* from slaughterhouses in animals examined only by

adspection, in 2024, one case of alveocystis in wild boar liver was also reported, which was identified by PCR method as the type *Echinococcus multilocularis*.

In 2024, the monitoring of foxes, which are the main reservoir and key source of alveolar echinococci infection for humans in Slovakia, was not carried out. As a result, it is not possible to evaluate the current geographical distribution or determine the prevalence trend of this parasite in Slovakia.

40. *Taenia* spp.

Taeniasis is a parasitic disease caused by tapeworms parasitizing the intestines of vertebrates, including humans. In the intestines of their final hosts, they can grow to lengths ranging from a few millimetres to several metres. Humans become infected through contaminated food, mainly by consuming raw or undercooked meat and contaminated water. The infection may be asymptomatic or may cause mild stomach and intestinal discomfort. Some types can also affect the brain and cause seizures, increased intracranial pressure, vomiting, headaches, visual disturbances, and mental disorders. Bovine cysticercosis is caused by the larva of the tapeworm *Taenia saginata* and porcine cysticercosis by the larva of the tapeworm *Taenia solium*, which develops in the muscles and organs of animals and grows into an adult tapeworm in the human intestine after consumption of contaminated meat by humans.

During 2024, one case of teniasis was reported. The last case of taeniasis was registered in 2022.

The detection of cysticerci in slaughterhouses in pigs and cattle is rare in Slovakia. In 2023, no positive findings of cysticerci in cattle or pigs were reported, and in 2024, 374,262 head of cattle and pigs were surveyed. Morbidity was confirmed in four pigs.

41. *Toxocara* spp.

Toxocariasis is one of the most widespread parasitic diseases of carnivores; it is caused by parasitic worms – roundworms of the *Toxocara* genus. Adult individuals of the *Toxocara* genus live in the small intestine of dogs, cats, and other carnivores. The eggs of the parasite excreted in droppings remain infectious for several years. In humans, larvae capable of surviving in tissues develop in the digestive tract after ingestion of the eggs but do not mature to the adult stage. Risk factors involve close contact with dogs, cats, or soil, or eating raw meat and drinking untreated water. Toxocariasis occurs worldwide and is linked to the presence of the final host. The highest seroprevalence is reported in the African region and the lowest in the Eastern Mediterranean region.

In 2024, a total of eight cases were reported (a morbidity rate of 0.15/100 000) under the diagnosis B83.0 Visceral larva migrans – toxocariasis, which represents four fewer cases than last year.

In 2024, 178 people were serologically tested for the presence of antibodies against *Toxocara* spp. at the Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences. Antibodies were not detected in any of the individuals tested.

In 2024, 3 628 samples of faeces and intestinal contents from definitive hosts of roundworms of the genus *Toxocara* and *Toxascaris* were examined. 7.94% of samples were found to be positive for roundworms and their eggs, which is the lowest percentage in the last 10 years. The most significant decline in prevalence was observed in the dogs. The prevalence of toxocariasis in examined animals in Slovakia has ranged between 7.94% and 12.6% over the last 10 years.

42. *Trichinella* spp.

Nematodes of the *Trichinella* genus cause a serious parasitic disease – trichinosis – in animals and humans. The main reservoir of the parasite in Slovakia is the red fox, and it is endemic in eastern and central Slovakia. The most common source of infection for humans is

wild boar or domestic pigs, but cases of infections in humans after consuming horse and dog meat have also been reported. In 2023, 76 cases of trichinellosis were reported in EU countries (including 14 hospitalisations), with no deaths reported. Most cases came from Croatia, Romania, and France. Compared to data from the period 2018 to 2022, trichinellosis in humans does not show a significant upward or downward trend.

During 2024, two cases of the disease were reported (a morbidity rate of 0.04/100,000), with no cases reported last year. Before 2024, the last reported clinical case of trichinellosis was in a man in 2017 (his medical history indicated consumption of wild game sausage). At the Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, 203 blood sera samples from patients suspected of having tissue helminthiasis were tested for trichinellosis as part of differential diagnosis. The presence of antibodies to *Trichinella* spp. was confirmed in two persons (1%).

A total of 439,940 animals were tested for *Trichinella* spp., all with negative results.

43. *Anisakis* spp.

Anisakis nematodes are parasites of saltwater fish that pass through up to three intermediate hosts. Although they rarely reach adulthood in humans and are usually spontaneously eliminated from the digestive tract within three weeks of infection, the *Anisakis simplex* parasite causes severe allergic reactions in humans. These parasites are often found in the flesh of cod, plaice, salmon, herring, and monkfish. The disease is transmitted via raw, undercooked, or insufficiently frozen fish meat or shellfish. If unfrozen fish is stored on ice, the larvae migrate from the intestines and liver to the muscle tissue of the fish, which increases the likelihood of infection even from gutted fish and fish fillets. In 2023, among EU countries, five outbreaks of anisakiasis were reported in France. The presumed place of exposure for four of the five outbreaks involving 28 cases was “school and kindergarten”, i.e., public catering facilities. No hospitalisations or deaths were reported.

In 2024, as in previous years, no disease caused by *Anisakis simplex* roundworms was reported in humans.

Twenty-three samples were examined for the presence of visible larvae of the *Anisakidae* family, with positive findings reported in two samples originating from Norway and Spain.

44. *Dirofilaria* spp.

Dirofilariasis is a disease caused by parasitic hairworms of the species *Dirofilaria (D.) immitis* and *D. repens* of the family *Onchocercidae*. The main hosts are dogs, cats, and wild carnivores. Among the hosts and vectors are different species of mosquitoes. Adults of *D. immitis* are most commonly found in the cardiac atrium and ventricle, pulmonary arteries, and the vena cava of the definitive host. The disease manifests itself with coughing, shortness of breath, and eventually heart and kidney failure. Clinical signs depend on the amount of the parasite occurring in the host organism. The human host is non-specific; the subacute form is characterised by the formation of subcutaneous nodules on the head, eyelid, face, neck, and chest. In the pulmonary form of infection, 1 to 3 cm lesions are formed in the lungs.

In 2024, no new cases of human dirofilariasis were reported.

Since 2005, dog blood samples are tested for the presence of dirofilariasis. In 2024, 536 dogs were tested, with a positivity rate of 21.83%. While in previous years infections with *D. repens* were predominant, since 2022 there has been an alarming increase in the proportion of mono-infections with *D. immitis*, which may lead to heart failure in dogs and a fatal ending. The increasing proportion of *D. immitis* is evidenced not only by the increased number of findings of this parasites in dogs, but also by the first *D. immitis* infection in humans, which was reported in 2021. What is interesting is the sudden shift in the prevalence of *D. immitis* and *D. repens* from 2021 (until then, *D. repens* had been dominant) to 2022 (since then, significantly dominant is *D. immitis*).

Although the climate change in Slovakia during the period 2021–2023 was not extreme in terms of a sudden change, the long-term warming trend and some specific anomalies during this period might have created significantly more favourable conditions for the spread of this *D. immitis*, which naturally prevails in warm and subtropics regions. According to data from the Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute, the average annual temperature in 2022 was by 1.5°C higher than in the reference period of 1991–2020. February of 2022 was warmer than average by 2 to 3.5°C – in most parts of the territory, it was even “significantly above average”, and the summer of 2022 was among the warmest in measurement history. The following year, 2023, was the second warmest year since 1931 (just behind 2014), and September 2023 was the warmest September in the history of measurements. A prolonged period of temperatures above 14°C (optimally above 18°C) is critical for the development of *D. immitis* larvae in mosquitoes – these conditions significantly prolonged the vector season in 2022 and 2023. Warm winters and early springs (e.g., the warm February of 2022) enabled mosquitoes to become active earlier, resulting in an earlier and more continuous cycle of parasite transmission. The record-breaking hot summer of 2022, as well as the strong summer and September of 2023, created an optimal environment for mosquito reproduction and transmission of infectious *D. immitis*.

45. Usutu virus

The Usutu virus is an arbovirus from the family *Flaviviridae*, which is related to the West Nile virus. It was first identified in Africa (Swaziland, 1959), and the virus was named after the Usutu River. In Europe, the main carrier of the Usutu virus is the mosquito (*Culex pipiens*). The Usutu virus cycle involves complex interactions between mosquitoes and particularly birds. Humans are occasionally infected by mosquito bites, but they do not play a significant role in maintaining the virus in nature. The main bird hosts of the virus are blackbirds, magpies, and some owls. The incubation period of the virus is 3 to 12 days. Most people infected with the Usutu virus are asymptomatic. Symptoms of Usutu virus infection may include mild fever, rash, and jaundice. In some cases, encephalitis and meningoencephalitis may occur. Over the past two decades, the virus has spread across much of the European continent, leading to significant morbidity and mortality in birds, with a marked resurgence of bird infections recorded across Europe in recent years.

Until 2019, 46 cases of Usutu virus infection in humans had been reported in Europe. The cases were mostly asymptomatic, with most of them being identified randomly in donated blood samples. There is no specific antiviral treatment or vaccine for Usutu fever. Prevention consists of protection against mosquito bites.

In 2024, the first two autochthonous cases of Usutu fever were reported in humans from the Nitra Region, in the Nové Zámky District. The Usutu virus was confirmed in captured mosquitoes as well as in mosquito saliva in selected locations in Slovakia.

46. Zika virus

The Zika virus is an arbovirus from the *Flaviviridae* family, transmitted mainly by mosquitoes of the genus *Aedes*. The Zika virus was first isolated in 1947 in Uganda. Since then, the virus has spread from Africa to the American continent. The main mechanism of transmission is mosquito bites. Ways of transmission in humans, such as transplacental transmission, blood transfusion, and sexual transmission, have been reported. The incubation period of the disease is 3–14 days. In 80% of infected individuals, the infection is asymptomatic. Symptoms include fever, rash, joint pain, conjunctivitis, and headache. If the mother is infected during pregnancy, newborns may develop microcephaly. The teratogenic effects of the Zika virus were confirmed in 2016 in South America during a major epidemic. There is no specific antiviral treatment or vaccine for Zika fever. Prevention consists of protection against mosquito bites.

In 2019, the first three autochthonous cases of Zika fever were reported in EU/EEA countries, specifically in France.

The first imported cases of Zika fever were reported in 2016. After seven years without any cases of the disease, one case was reported in 2024 (a morbidity rate of 0.02/100,000).

Annex 1

List of Cooperating Organisations

- Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development of the Slovak Republic – National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with the EFSA in the SR
- National Agricultural and Food Centre – Food Research Institute
- National Reference Centre for Salmonellosis, Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
- National Reference Centre for Campylobacteriosis, Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
- National Reference Centre for Toxoplasmosis at the Regional Public Health Authority in Banská Bystrica
- National Reference Centre for Vibrionaceae, at the Regional Public Health Authority in Komárno
- National Reference Centre for Legionella, National Reference Centre for Viral Hepatitis, National Reference Centre for Enteric Virus Identification of the Faculty of Medicine, Slovak Medical University
- National Institute of Tuberculosis, Pulmonary Diseases and Thoracic Surgery, Vyšné Hágy
- Regional Public Health Authority in Banská Bystrica
- Regional Public Health Authority in Bratislava
- Regional Public Health Authority in Komárno
- Regional Public Health Authority in Košice
- Regional Public Health Authority in Nitra and the team from Laboratories of the Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic at Regional Public Health Authority in Nitra
- Regional Public Health Authority in Poprad
- Regional Public Health Authority in Prešov
- Regional Public Health Authority in Prievidza
- Regional Public Health Authority in Trenčín
- Regional Public Health Authority in Trnava
- Regional Public Health Authority in Žilina
- Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, v. v. i., in Košice
- Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava, Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
- Slovak Medical University in Bratislava
- State Veterinary and Food Administration of the Slovak Republic
- State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute in Bratislava
- State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute in Dolný Kubín
- State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary and Food Institute in Košice
- State Veterinary and Food Institute – Veterinary Institute in Zvolen
- Comenius University, Faculty of Medicine, Institute of Epidemiology, Bratislava
- Comenius University, Jessenius Faculty of Medicine in Martin
- University of Pavol Jozef Šafárik in Košice, Institute of Epidemiology
- University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
- University Hospital in Martin, Department of Infectious Diseases and Travel Medicine
- Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
- Institute of Parasitology of the Slovak Academy of Sciences, v. v. i., in Bratislava
- Water Management Research Institute, Bratislava

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Annex 3
List of abbreviations

ARO	Acute Respiratory Disease
BA	Bratislava
BB	Banská Bystrica
BSE	Bovine Spongiform Encephalopathy
CBRN	Chemical, Biological, Radiological, Nuclear
CJch	Creutzfeldt-Jacob Disease
ČOV	Wastewater Treatment Plant
DK	Dolný Kubín
DSS	Social Care Home
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
EEA	European Economic Area
EFSA	European Food Safety Authority
EFTA	European Free Trade Association
EHEC	Enterohaemorrhagic <i>E.coli</i>
EHP	European Economic Area
EPEC	Enteropathogenic <i>E. coli</i>
EPIS	Epidemiological information system
EREN	EFSA's Scientific Network on Sudden Risks
ES	European Community
EU	European Union
EÚ/EHP	European Economic Area
EVs	Enteroviruses
FCHPT	Faculty of Chemical and Food Technology
HD	Cattle
HFRS	Haemorrhagic Fever With Renal Syndrome
HPAI	<i>highly pathogenic avian influenza</i>
HUS	Haemolytic Uraemic Syndrome
dis.	Morbidity
CHPO	influenza-like disease
IEV	Enterovirus infection
IgG	Immunoglobulin G
ISBN	International Standard Book Number
JLF UK	Jessenius Faculty of Medicine in Martin, Comenius University
KE	Košice
KN	Komárno
KoNS	Coagulase Negative Staphylococci
KPS	Coagulase Positive Staphylococci
LB	Lyme borreliosis
LCH	Legionnaire's disease
LF	Faculty of Medicine
LF SZU	Faculty of Medicine, Slovak Medical University in Bratislava)

LF UK	Faculty of Medicine of Comenius University Bratislava
MIÚ	Microbiology Institute
MRSA	Methicillin-resistant <i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>
nešp.	Unspecified
NKB EFSA in the SR	National Contact Point for Scientific and Technical Cooperation with EFSA
NoV	Norwalk virus
NP	National Park
NPPC – VÚP	National Agricultural and Food Centre – Food Research Institute
nvCJch	new variant of Creutzfeldt-Jacob disease
NPEV	non-polio enteroviruses
NR	Nitra
NRC	National Reference Centre
NRC IEV	National Reference Centre for Enteric Virus Identification
NRC LEG	National Reference Centre for Legionella in the Environment Public Health Authority of the SR
NRL	National Reference Laboratory
NÚDCH	National Institute of Children's Diseases
NÚTPCHaHCH	National Institute of Tuberculosis, Pulmonary Diseases and Thoracic Surgery
OV	Wastewater
PCH	Prion diseases
PO	Prešov
PaÚ SAV	Institute of Parasitology, Slovak Academy of Sciences
pr.	case
PV	Poliovirus
RL	Reference laboratory
RNA	Ribonucleic acid
RT PCR	Real time PCR – polymerase chain reaction with reverse transcription
RÚVZ	Regional Public Health Authority
SARI	Severe Acute Respiratory Infection
SAS	Slovak Academy of Sciences
SHMÚ	Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute
SL	Test laboratory
s.l.	<i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i> sensu lato complex
SR	Slovak Republic
STU	Slovak University of Technology
ŠVPS SR	State Veterinary and Food Administration of the Slovak Republic
ŠVPÚ	State Veterinary and Food Institute
SZU	Slovak Medical University
TBC	tuberculosis
TBEV	Tick-borne encephalitis virus
ÚE	Institute of Epidemiology

UK	Comenius University
TSE	Transmissible spongiform encephalopathy
TÚV	Warm utility water
UNB	University Hospital Bratislava
UNLP	Louis Pasteur University Hospital in Kosice
ÚKSÚP	Central Control and Testing Institute in Agriculture Bratislava
UVLF KE	University of Veterinary Medicine and Pharmacy in Košice
ÚVZ SR	Public Health Authority of the Slovak Republic
VHA	Hepatitis A virus
VHE/HEV	Hepatitis E virus
VirÚ BMC SAV	Institute of Virology, Biomedical Centre of the Slovak Academy of Sciences
VPO	Veterinary prevention and protection plan
VPÚ	Veterinary and Food Institute
VÚ	Veterinary Institute
VTEC/STEC	Verotoxin/shigatoxin producing <i>E.coli</i>
VÚP	Food Research Institute
VÚVH	Water Management Research Institute
WB	Western Blot
WHO	World Health Organization
WNV	West Nile virus
ZA	Žilina
ZV	Zvolen

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